

A Transdisciplinary perspective of the *Message* of Fernando Pessoa

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Resumo

Este ensaio transdisciplinar sobre a *Mensagem* do poeta Fernando Pessoa, uma das obras mais relevantes da literatura Portuguesa, é uma contribuição sobre a atual situação de guerra na Ucrânia, depois da pandemia de Covid-19.

Résumé

Cet essai transdisciplinaire sur le *Message* du poète Fernando Pessoa, l'une des œuvres les plus pertinentes de la littérature portugaise, est une contribution sur la situation de guerre actuelle en Ukraine, après la pandémie de Covid-19.

Abstract

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This transdisciplinary essay on the *Message* of the poet Fernando Pessoa, one of the most relevant works of Portuguese literature, is a contribution on the current war situation in Ukraine, after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Third Part of Message

Pax in excelsis

The Hidden One

What fecund symbol

Comes in the anxious dawn?

*On the dead Cross of the World,
Life, which is the Rose.*

What divine symbol

Is borne by the day now seen?

*On the Cross, which is Destiny,
The Rose, which is Christ.*

What final symbol

Is shown by the sun now risen?

*On the dead and fatal Cross,
The Rose of the Hidden One.*

Fernando Pessoa was a poet that wrote the work entitled *Message* [1]. The third part of *Message* [2] begins with the Latin epigraph “Pax in excelsis” which means that the content conveyed by the *Message* is one of peace, so necessary for the current time of post-pandemic and the war in Ukraine. In these verses, it is stated that “Life, which is the Rose... The Rose of the Hidden One” and one of its symbolisms refers to the Life of the soul that exists within every human being, regardless of race, culture, gender, etc.

It is this One Life that binds us all on a deeper level and it is manifested by each one of us on Earth.

For its side, in transdisciplinarity the Hidden Third is a-logical term located in the area of non-resistance and non-time – a discontinuous leap between the levels of Reality – corresponding to the sacred that is symbolized by some Christian thinkers, like Pessoa, as the Cross and the Rose. We also have an area of resistance, located in time, between the various levels of Reality, where the logical included third unites contradictories (consciousness-matter, divinity-nature, unity-diversity, complexity-simplicity). The Hidden Third is the one that gives meaning to the included third.

Basarab Nicolescu [3] refers that:

“transdisciplinarity means transgression of duality, opposing binary pairs and this duality is transcended by the open unity that encompasses both the universe and the human being. The Hidden Third, in its relationship with the levels of Reality, is fundamental for the understanding of ‘unus mundus’ described by cosmopolitanism.... In the transdisciplinary approach, or trans-Reality, the Subject and the Object are immersed in the Hidden Third.”

Basarab Nicolescu also stated that “until Modernity, Subject and Object were totally separated, and the notion of dominance of the Subject over the Object were exalted” having this perspective be defended by the Cartesian paradigm [4]. This is characterized by a binary partition (Subject versus Object) where the complex was reduced to simple through a process designated “blind intelligence” by Edgar Morin [5]. For its side, the introduction of levels of Reality in transdisciplinarity, a kind of Jacob’s ladder of the theological field [6], is an image of the scale of consciousness of being that Fernando Pessoa described in the verses “What fecund symbol / Comes in the anxious dawn?,... What divine symbol/Is borne by the day now seen?... What final symbol / Is shown by the sun now risen?” that refer to the various stages of the day (dawn, end of day, and new day) as a symbol of the different levels of consciousness of the human being.

In summary, some recent research in the intersection of science and spirituality shows that the evolution of species, namely the human one, depends on the strength of the group and the power of altruism in which the network of the group is benefited by the conscious acts of its members [7]. **T**

References

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